

AN INVESTIGATION INTO HUFU BUSINESS ENGLISH LEARNERS' DIFFICULTIES WITH TASK - BASED LANGUAGE TEACHING APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

English is the only language that is globally understood. Having employees with little or no English language skills is a barrier. Overcoming this barrier can only be done by recruiting staff having good English communicative competence. Consequently, English is considered a requirement for all job applicants. English learning and teaching, therefore, has undergone a lot of changes accordingly to meet the demand of modern employers. While a number of teaching methods have been proposed in an effort to enhance the teaching and learning effectiveness, Task – Based Language Teaching (TBLT) is considered a good solution which can bring the most satisfied results as learners can experience the use of language in real contexts, especially in Business English classroom. By learning English through using, learners can learn not only the linguistic aspect of the language but also how to use it in contextualized situations. However, the implementation of TBLT is not without any problems, not mentioning the institution's own characteristics and conditions. In order that the introduction of TBLT works well in HUFU setting, it is necessary to dissect difficulties HUFU students may face while using the target language to perform different tasks. Within the time frame and condition, this research only tries to investigate students' problems in order to make most of TBLT in HUFU Business English class. The author also hopes that the finding of her study can help to enhance the learning and teaching of Business English in HUFU. As a result, HUFU students can be well equipped with English communication skills – the most powerful soft skill in the world Business arena nowadays.

Key words: Task - Based Language Teaching, Business English

1 INTRODUCTION

With the globalization of trade and economy, English has been widely accepted as the international language of communication. English, nowadays, is considered as an essential soft skill for job seekers. Consequently, the demand for English is increasing incessantly. The lack of the language and communication skills would certainly restrict their development or adversely affect their professional success and financial welfare in a certain manner. As for university graduates, to become competitive in the job market, they have to demonstrate possession of adequate linguistic and communication skills in English to function effectively at workplace. “To furnish students this international communication medium” has become the goal of almost all English courses at Vietnamese University.

At Ho Chi Minh University of Food Industry (hereafter abbreviated as HUFU), General English courses have been introduced to students with an aim to develop students' communicative competence. Although a lot of effort has been made, the teaching and learning results are still far from satisfactory. One of the major reasons account for this lies in the teaching method.

Obviously, in order to equip students with the language they need at workplace, the learning and teaching should prepare them for the content and tasks which they will be exposed in their professional life. In other word, students should be exposed to real communication contexts. Task – Based Language Teaching (TBLT), which employs communicative task as the basis unit is believed to respond best to this requirement. By learning English through using, learners can learn not only the linguistic aspect of the language but also how to use it in contextualized situations. Consequently, TBLT has been implemented in the author's class at HUFU with an aim to allow her students to practise the language they will need in their workplace. However, the implementation of TBLT is not without any problems, not mentioning the institution's own characteristics and conditions. In order that the introduction of TBLT works well in HUFU setting, it is necessary to dissect difficulties HUFU students are facing while using the target language to perform different tasks in their class.

A research question that guides the study: What are HUFU students' difficulties with TBLT approach?

2 BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

The General English course at HUFU is a compulsory course for all students. This course lasts 4 semesters with 45 periods for each. The aim of the course is to develop students' communicative competence. Life (A1-A2 and A2-B1) is employed as the course book. The total number of 24 units is covered in 4 semesters. All the students begin this course in the second semester of their first year at university because the first semester is reserved at the gap time for those who does not pass the placement exam to take part in an extra course. This extra course aims to equip students some basic knowledge of English and English communication skills. The total amount of time for it is 45 periods. The students' language proficiency is assessed in 4 - skills tests during and at the end of the semester.

The students are divided into groups of about 40 students which help teachers and students have more opportunities for interactions. However, the unmovable seats can hardly support group activities in English communicative class.

The student population mentioned in this research includes 26 males (35.1%) and 48 (64.9.4%) females of different majors at HUFU. Their ages range from 19-20. The majority of students 75.6% (56) started learning English when they were in junior high school. Another 14.4% (18) students began to learn English at primary school. This figure emphasizes that a big number of the target students has good knowledge of English before they start their compulsory English course at HUFU. All of them have a strong motivation to learn English for their future job and regard it to be very important. The problem is that in spite of studying English as a subject, they do not get exposure to situations where they can use English or they can observe how English is

used by others. Besides, being guided by the test – oriented learning and teaching practice at high school, they may be highly competent in term of linguistics but most of them have poor English communicative ability.

3 RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

The data collection instrument is a set of questionnaires for the students. The questionnaire was developed based on the literature review and informal conversations with the researchers' students. The students' questionnaire is constructed for the purpose of gathering data on the students' learning needs and their problems with TBLT. The questionnaire consists of two parts. The first part would help the researcher to gain the students' personal information (age, sex, educational background). These pieces of information are needed to establish profiles of the students participating in the study. The second part of the students' questionnaire includes 8 questions, each of which is presented in an understandable and easy way for the informants to mark their choice.

4 LITERATURE REVIEW

4.1 Task – Based Language Teaching

As David Nunan (1991) says, "Task based teaching and learning is teaching and learning a language by using language to accomplish open ended tasks. Learners are given a problem or objective to accomplish but are left with some freedom in approaching this problem or objective." The underlying principles of TBLT are:

Emphasize on learning progress, not learning result

Learn language through interactive activities.

Facilitate learning progress

language can be used in learner's daily life

Student has chances to input and output the language

4.2 Task definition

Richards, Platt & Weber (1985) suggest that a task is: an activity or action which is carried out as the result of processing or understanding language (i.e. as a response), for example: drawing a map while listening to a tape, listening to an instruction and performing a command. A task may or may not involve the production of language and it usually requires the teacher to clarify what will be regarded as successful completion of the task. The purpose of using of a variety of different kinds of tasks in language teaching is to make teaching more communicative because it provides a purpose for a classroom activity which goes beyond the practice of language for its own sake.

Besides, the pedagogical task defined by Nunan (1989) is of practical sense, as well. He describes a task as "*a piece of classroom work which involves learners in comprehending, manipulating, producing or interacting in the target language while their attention is focused on mobilizing*

their grammatical knowledge to express meaning and their intention is to convey meaning rather than to manipulate form. The task should also have a sense of completeness, being able to stand alone as a communicative act in its own right with a beginning, a middle and an end". Task here equals communicative activity which involves using language to acquire and express meaning in order to achieve a particular purpose and the meaning rather than language forms is primarily focused.

Willis is another figure who contributes to the use of tasks in language classroom. She (1996) states that a task is a goal-oriented activity. To achieve the outcome (goal), learners need to use the target language for communication. Although the focus is on the outcome of the activity rather than on the language, the language is seen as the vehicle to bring about the outcome through the exchange of meanings.

Although the definitions vary somewhat, most of them emphasize the primacy of meaning: the learners' attention should be directed toward meaning exchange in order to arrive at an outcome other than that of learning a specified feature of the language. The outcome can be a decision, a solution to a problem, an agreement reached among participants. This rules out activities which, though involving exchange of information, do not result in a specific outcome such as telling a story, questions and answers as independent tasks though they can be part of a task. Pedagogically, tasks is deployed in classrooms to facilitate meaningful interaction and offer the learner opportunities to process meaningful input and produce meaningful output in order to reach relevant and obtainable goals. In other words, tasks invite the learner to act primarily as a language user and not as a language learner. Tasks are supposed to elicit the kinds of communicative behaviour that naturally arises from performing real-life language tasks because these are believed to foster language acquisition.

Besides, these definitions also suggest that, the things learners do with the target language in the classroom should be related to or derived from what the learners are supposed to be able to do with the target language in the real world. Learning Task should resemble an outside-world task insofar as it requires interaction among participants and the application of all abilities and cognitive processes involved in actual language use.

Based on the way most researchers define and use the term and the actual examples people give in their discussion of task-based language teaching, some defining features of tasks are outlined below.

*Tasks are goal-directed activities

*Task completion engages learners in using the language communicatively

*A primary focus on meaning is involved

*There is a close link between the tasks performed by learners in the language classroom and in the outside world

*the assessment of the task is in terms of outcome.

These defining features are the necessary conditions an activity has to meet to be considered as a task.

4.3 Task components

Nunan recommends analyzing or categorizing tasks according to their goals, input data, activities, settings and roles. The goals, input and activities are used for task analysis, and the roles and settings are implied by the task.

Goals refer to the general intention for the learning task. They serve as a guideline in the overall process of task performance and provide the point of contact between the learning task and the real world target task. In other words, the goals of a particular learning task are dictated by the purposes for performing the task in the real world. These goals represent the communicative, affective or cognitive aspects of a given target task (Nunan 1989). A complex task involving a range of activities may have a number of goals, from general to specific one. To motivate learners to engage in the task, goals should reflect their needs and interest.

Input is defined as the data that learners are to work on when performing a task. It may be linguistic (e.g. an article, a weather forecast, a radio news, etc) or non-linguistic (pictures, photos, charts, maps, ect). In fact, input data can be derived from a wide range of sources in a real world context. Nunan (1999) argues that the authenticity of data will provide the learner with naturally occurring language with no loss of context. Input forms the point of departure for the task, thus it must be comprehensible and interesting for learners to motivate them to move to the next stage of the task. According to Brown and Yule (1983 as cited in Jeon & Hahn, 2002) dialogue texts (linguistic data) containing description or instruction are much easier for learners to comprehend and manipulate than non-dialogue texts, which include arguments or abstract concepts.

Teacher and learner roles TBLT classrooms make use of the principles of student-centered approach, thus it suggests a redefining of role relationship of learner and teacher vis-à-vis traditional approach. The role of the learner in a task-based class is central. It is the learners doing things most of the times, under the guidance of the instructor. They also interact mainly with other learners in the group and learn through cooperation with other learners with less reliance on teacher, and actively engages in negotiating meaning. In brief, they should be responsible for their own learning.

Setting includes the physical environment in which the task takes place, as well as the classroom arrangement specified by the tasks, or in other words, the basic groupings, i.e. teacher-fronted, pair work, group work or individuals.

Feedback concerns task evaluation which may be done by the teachers or by the learners themselves. Appropriate evaluation from teachers and their peers not only facilitate the learners' communication skills but also motivate them to make more progress. However, a question emerges is how feedback can be optimally related to changes in participant behavior. According to Johnson and Johnson (1994, as cited in Jeon and Hahn, 2002), a carefully designed peer assessment should provide support as well as challenging their group members to realize their potential. For teachers, feedback not only including correction, comment, support, etc in class but also the general assessment of the task performance (Bachman, 2002 as cited in Jeon and Hahn, 2002).

5 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Students' difficulties with task goals.

The result of Question 3 shows that almost the guidelines are clear for almost all the students (62/74). This is quite understandable because the teacher always try to clarify all her requirements and move around to help her students when necessary. As her students' English is not very good, she has to make a demonstration. She, sometimes, even have to explain the guidelines in Vietnamese to make sure that her learners know what to do, how to do.

However, a big number of students (49/74) thinks that the goals of the tasks are not very relevant to their needs and interest. 4 of them even think that they not relevant. It is not surprising because of topic in the course are related to academic. Even though the teacher herself try to create a goal to respond to the students' learning needs to motivate them and get them more involved in performing the tasks, she can not change the topic in the course book.

5.2 Students' difficulties with task inputs

In respond to question 5, which aims to explore students' problems with the task inputs, a majority of students 57/74 believe that the data provided to them is comprehensible but not very interesting. Obviously, limited time is account for this weakness. Apart from the one in the course book, the teacher also collected data from different sources such as news paper, video clips, website, photos... . Despite her effort, the data sources are not available for all the tasks. Furthermore, there is not much time in the class and students' English knowledge is limited, priority has been given to the one that is easier to understand. This limitation, undeniably may affect students' motivation in task performance greatly.

5.3 Students' difficulties with teachers and learners' role.

Most students are familiar with the traditional learning and teaching method at high school where they are passive listeners and note-takers. Their teachers are the source of knowledge, thus, control and monitor the learning process in class. With this new teaching approach, students are the controllers of their own learning. Consequently, most of them (61/74) are not familiar to exploring and getting information themselves. Besides, task performance requires a lot of group work while a big number of learners have problems with it. In replying to question 6, 63 out of 74 suggested that they and their partners lack of skills for group work. While only few (9/74) of them find their partners uncooperative, many of them (42/74) find their partners' English not good enough. 39 respondents even do not feel self – confident with their English as well. Their language knowledge, clearly, hinder their task performance effectiveness.

The findings of question 6 further indicate that time allocation for doing tasks is another barrier for the learners. As close talk to 5 groups of around 17 students reveal that they need to spend a big amount of time to make reference because they can not express what they want to say in many cases and they do not have enough experience to do all the tasks. They are sometimes not sure if they do appropriately. While time is too short, they can not always seek the teacher's help as she is busy with other groups.

5.4 Students' difficulties with task setting.

Long (1989) states that the grouping of participants along with task-group interactions is an essential element influencing the communicative interactions and learning outcomes of the tasks. Researchers have found that group work increases both the quantity and quality of language production, giving the learners an opportunity to experiment with the language and negotiate for meaning in a non-threatening environment. Therefore, classroom arrangement should be flexible to motivate learners to participate in tasks.

However, the results of research question 6 and an informal talk with students show that one big hinderance to task performance mentioned by 69/74 students is the class arrangement. It is not surprising because all of the seats are unmovable. All the desks are closely arranged. Consequently, it is difficult for them to move around or to group conveniently for task performance. In additions, the noise from the groups nearby also distracts and affects other groups' attention.

5.5 Students' difficulties with task feedback

Feedback is very important for language learners. Their learning progress will be facilitated if they receive frequent and useful feedback on their performance. Students will learn more if they get correction from both their teacher and their peers. Peer feedbacks not only help to ease the teacher's burden in giving feedback to their students but also promote their critical thinking skills and collaborative skills. Furthermore, to make suggestions, students must recognize their peers' mistakes and become critical learners.

Findings of question 7 and 8 indicate that a considerable number of respondents (27/74) find their friends' feedback not very helpful while all of them confirm that they improve much from their teacher's comment.

Through an informal talk with 5 groups of students, the researcher learnt that while they are not self – confident with their language knowledge, some are not very happy with their friends' feedback although they agreed that they did learn from their friends. A number of reasons given include: most of their friends' English is not much better, they peers do not have experience in dealing with different tasks, they learn much more from the teacher. A possible explanation for this problem is that students are still not familiar with independent learning. They were knowledge receivers for a long time at high school. Their limited language competence also makes many of them feel less confident in the effectiveness of peer correction activities. Constraint of time in class is another factor which makes them feel under pressure of learning as much as they can. Consequently, they may find it is quicker to learn from their instructor

Conclusion and recommendation

This research has been done with the aim to explore HUFIL learners' perception of major difficulties with Task – Based Language instruction. The findings obtained from analyzing the data shows that although HUFIL students have favorable attitude toward TBLT, they are still facing many challenges while performing tasks in class. In order to enhance the effectiveness of

Task – Based instruction, a number of suggestions are made. First, the topics taught should be more relevant to students' needs. Although English is academically instructed in HUFU, a deep analysis of students' learning needs is necessary to address it appropriately. While many of them only want to learn English for future job, academic - learning orientation may hinder their learning effort. Besides, the library system should be upgraded to help teachers and students in getting more interesting materials for input. An investment in modern language learning equipment such as listening devices, movable chairs, also should be made. Last but not least, training of learners should be provided. In TBLT class, the learners have to take control of the learning activities. They have to work independently and actively under the guide and help of the teacher. This is in contrast to the traditional class where the learner is dependent, for most of his learning, on his teacher. Therefore, a shift from a teacher-centred approach to a learner-centred approach requires some adaptation for those who are accustomed to passive learning style, otherwise it can result in unproductive learning experience for the learners. Further more, pair work and group work is one of the major features of TBLT but according to Nunan's experience (2005), many students hold positive attitude to it but they do not know how to do. Thus, it is necessary to train learners to prepare them for such an experience where they can take control of their own learning.

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APPENDIX

QUESTIONNAIRE TO THE STUDENTS

This questionnaire is designed to explore the difficulties of English students at HUFİ. The collected information will be used in a research.

Please read all the questions carefully and circle the appropriate choice or choices.

Thank you very much for your cooperation.

Part I: ABOUT YOU

1. Age:
2. Gender:
 - a. Male
 - b. Female
3. You have learned English since you were in
 - a. University
 - b. Senior secondary school
 - c. Junior secondary school
 - Others (Please specify)

Part II: RESEARCH QUESTION

1. Why do you learn English?

- a. Because it is a compulsory subject
- b. To read professional literature
- c. For my future job
- d. Others

2. How important is English for your future job?

- a. Very important
- b. Important
- c. Not very important
- d. Not important

3. I understand the guidelines for each task

- a. Clearly
- b. not very clearly
- c. not clearly

4. In my opinion, the goals of the tasks are to my needs and interests

- a. relevant
- b. not very relevant
- c. not relevant

5. What do you think about the data provided before you do the tasks?

- a. Comprehensible and interesting
- b. Comprehensible but not very interesting
- c. Not very comprehensible but interesting
- d. Neither comprehensible nor interesting

6. What problems do you often have while performing tasks in class (you can select more than one choice)?

- a. It is difficult to move around.
- b. Your partners are not cooperative.
- c. Your partners' English is not good
- d. Your English is not good enough to perform assigned tasks
- e. You and your partners are not familiar to group work
- f. Getting information myself
- g. Others.....

7. What do you think of your friends' feedback?

- a. Very useful
- b. Useful
- c. Not very useful
- d. Not useful

8. What do you think of your teacher's feedback?

- a. Very useful
- b. Useful
- c. Not very useful
- d. Not useful